

A Comparative Study Of Air Quality Indices At A Rural Town In Andhra Pradesh

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Abstract— Air Quality Index (AQI) is very helpful to guide the public and administrators by converting the ambient Air Quality (AAQ) into AQI. The associated health impacts can be easily interpreted with AQI, as it gives a single value representing the overall quality of ambient air. The AQI at Mylavaram, a rural town and mandal headquarters in NTR district of Andhra Pradesh is studied during March-April 2022. Four parameters, PM10, PM2.5, SO₂ and NO₂ are considered. Samples are collected on four days and the concentrations obtained are converted to AQI. It is noticed that (i) PM10 and PM2.5 are more significant than the gaseous pollutants (ii) The particulate concentrations are inversely proportion to ambient temperature (iii) PM10 is the dominant parameter that is defining the final AQI value. The highest AQI value obtained is 54.38, which can be classified as *Satisfactory* as per the latest model being used in India. The ambient air quality based on the other models is classified as *Very clean* to *Clean*. It implies that the AAQ at Mylavaram is safe and is not severely polluted. This information is ascertained based on assimilative capacity of a criteria pollutant at Mylavaram. A code using C-programming is used to predict the air quality based on Gaussian and Plume rise models at Mylavaram due to the impact of a thermal power station located aerielly at 20km from Mylavaram. It is concluded that there is a plenty of assimilative capacity available at Mylavaram based on suspended particulates and SO₂. This further reiterates that Mylavaram air quality is safe during the period of study.

Keywords— Ambient Air Quality, Air Quality Index, Assimilative Capacity, Mylavaram, AQI Models, Gaussian Model

I. INTRODUCTION

The air we breathe should be clean for a happy health. Unfortunately, due to excessive industrialization, heavy use of automobiles, commercial utilities, Incinerators, open garbage burning, crop burning and other related aspects, the ambient air quality is deteriorating rapidly. The air pollutants travel a long distances based on the atmospheric stability and reach receptors at faraway places. It is becoming difficult to travel on the roads due to heavy exposure to the various gaseous and particulate pollutants. People who are allergic to the air pollutants are the major sufferers. It is important to have an alert mechanism to identify the level of air pollution in the atmosphere and warn the concerned public or administrators for the appropriate safety measures in this regard.

The Government of India through the Ministry of Environment & Forests and Climate Change launched Air Quality Index (AQI) in 2014 [1] with an objective to rank the ambient air quality that may impose severe health impacts on receiving population. A lot of exercise is made to study the available AQI models in different countries and finally arrived [2, 20] at an updated model that is presently being used. Few more studies are made in this direction to critically study the existing AQI models over a long period [20]. The AQI gives a representative number or index based on the actual concentrations of specific air pollutants at a locality. The concentrations are converted to a suitable Index based on simple to complex models [2, 3, 4, 5]. The associated health impacts based on the index value are also categorized. A low index value indicates air quality is clean and a very high value indicates the air quality is dangerous to health. The AQI will hence be helpful to the administrators to take precautionary measures or give safety warnings to the public. The public on the other hand will take necessary precautions while going outside if the ambient air is highly polluted. This will certainly help the older people and those who are having breathing and cardiovascular problems. For the benefit of the common public, *Paryavaran* - a mobile app is also available to identify the AQI value in the state of Andhra Pradesh.

Few studies are available to study the AQI values at a specific location [4, 6, 7, 8], at different locations in the country [9]. Studies are also available [10, 11, 12] for determining the change of air quality and/or AQI values during and after the COVID-19.

The major objective of the present study is to study the ambient air quality at Mylavaram, a rural area in NTR district of Andhra Pradesh, India, determine its AQI and the assimilative capacity. Mylavaram, the mandal headquarter of Mylavaram mandal, is a very busy town with a population of 21,763 and housing several commercial offices, a high school, Degree College, Engineering College besides several private Institutions offering education to the students in and around Mylavaram. Several people commute daily from Vijayawada, the nearest major city located at 40km, and few other major towns in the nearby vicinity for education, business and employment purposes. The present study is hence focused on the comparison of three AQI models for their application at this location. The assimilative capacity at the location due to the impact of a Thermal Power Station (NTTPS) located aeriually at 20km from Mylavaram is to be ascertained.

II. METHODOLOGY AND TOOLS USED

To compute the ambient air quality (AAQ), four parameters such as PM10, PM2.5, SO₂ and NO₂ are identified and are sampled. The ambient air sampling is carried out during March-April 2022. The analyzed values are converted to AQI values using the three AQI models as described below and compared. The AQI values obtained are also compared with that of AQI value developed at the location in a previous study [8] for comparison. The permissible values of the four parameters as per the guidelines adopted in India [13] is given in Table-1. The air pollutants from a thermal power plant will travel a long distances [14, 15, 16] due to the very tall stacks provided and poor stability conditions of atmosphere during nights and evenings.

TABLE 1
AAQ CONCENTRATION STANDARDS IN INDIA FOR THE PARAMETERS CONSIDERED IN THE STUDY

Parameter	Time weighted average	Concentration in ambient air, µg/m ³	
		Industrial, Residential, Rural and Other area	Ecologically sensitive area notified by the Central Government
Sulphur dioxide, µg/m ³	Annual	50	20
	24 hours	80	80
Nitrogen dioxide, µg/m ³	Annual	40	30
	24 hours	80	80
Particulate matter less than 10 µm or PM10	Annual	60	60
	24 hours	100	100
Particulate matter less than 2.5 µm or PM2.5	Annual	40	40
	24 hours	60	60

- Annual: Annual arithmetic average of minimum 104 measurements in a year at a particular site taken twice a week 24 hourly at uniform intervals
- 24 hours: 24 hours or 8 hours or I hour mentioned above as applicable shall be complied with 98% of time in a year, 2% of the time they may exceed the limits but not on two consecutive days of monitoring

AQI computation models

Three different models are considered in the present study. The computation approach using these models [2, 3, 4, 5] is discussed below and the interpretation of the AQI values based on these models and the associated health impacts are discussed in Table-3.

Model-1:

This is based on simple arithmetic ratio of pollutant concentration at the site to that prescribed and summation of all the pollutant values in a similar manner. Mathematically it is represented as

$$AQI = \frac{1}{n} \left[\sum_1^n \left(\frac{C_i}{C_s} \right) \right] \times 100 \text{ ----- (1)}$$

Where, $C_i/C_s = q$ and q is the air quality rating of any individual pollutant.

C_i = observed value of the parameter

C_s = standard value of recommended parameter

n = number of parameter considered

Model-2:

AQI is calculated by taking the logarithmic average of the ratio of the concentration of pollutants to the standard value of that pollutant. Mathematically it is represented as

$$\log(AQI) = \left(\frac{1}{n} [\log Q_1 + \log Q_2 + \dots + \log Q_n] \right) \text{ (2)}$$

Where, $Q_n = (C_n/C_s) \times 100$

Q_n = quality rating,

C_n = observed value of pollutant,

C_s = recommended value of pollutant,

n = number of pollutants considered

Model-3: IND-AQI approach

The sub-index (I) for a given pollutant concentration (C), as based on 'linear segmented principle' is calculated as:

$$I = \frac{I_{high} - I_{low}}{C_{high} - C_{low}} \times (C - C_{low}) + I_{low} \text{ ----- (3)}$$

C = the pollutant concentration

C_{low} = the concentration breakpoint that is $\leq C$

C_{high} = the concentration breakpoint that is $\geq C$

I_{low} = the index breakpoint corresponding to C_{low}

I_{high} = the index breakpoint corresponding to C_{high}

The Break points are categorized as per the following Table-2 for the Model-3. The AQI classifications for each of the models studied and the associated health impacts due to the AQI values are given in Table-3.

TABLE 2
LIMITS FOR THE BREAKPOINT CONCENTRATIONS FOR DETERMINING AQI USING MODEL-3

AQI Category (Range)	PM10 (24 hr)	PM2.5 (24 hr)	NO2 (24 hr)	SO2 (24 hr)
Good (0-50)	0-50	0-30	0-40	0-40
Satisfactory (51-100)	51-100	31-60	41-80	41-80
Moderately polluted (101-200)	101-250	61-90	81-180	81-380
Poor (201-300)	251-350	91-120	181-280	381-800
Very poor (301-400)	351-430	121-250	281-400	801-1600
Severe (401-500)	430+	250+	400+	1600+

TABLE 3
AQI CLASSIFICATIONS AND THE ASSOCIATED HEALTH IMPACTS

S. No	AQI value Limits			Associated health impacts of AQI values under Model-3
	Model-1	Model-2	Model-3	
1	Very Clean (<10)	Very Clean (<10)	Good (0-50)	Minimum Consequences
2	Clean (10-25)	Clean (10-25)	Satisfactory (51-100)	Sensitive persons may experience modest breathing difficulties.
3	Fairly Clean (25-50)	Fairly Clean (25-50)	Moderate (101-200)	People with lung disorders such as Asthma, heart problems, children, and the elderly may experience breathing difficulties.
4	Moderately Polluted (50-75)	Moderately Polluted (51-75)	Poor (201-300)	People who are exposed to it for an extended period of time may get respiratory difficulties. People with heart disorders are subjected to unnecessary exposure and pain.
5	Polluted (75-100)	Polluted (75-100)	Very poor (301-400)	People who are exposed for an extended period of time may develop respiratory illnesses. People with lung issues may see a stronger effect.
6	Heavily Polluted (>100)	Heavily Polluted (100-125)	Severe (401-500)	Even healthy people may experience respiratory effects, and patients with heart and lung disorders may experience major health consequences. Even mild physical exercise might have negative health consequences.
7		Severely Polluted (>125)		

It is noted that, there are six categories of AQI values in Models 1 & 3 while seven categories under Model-2. The classification of the categories under Models 1 & 2 are similar except that one extra category is added for AQI value greater than 125 in Model-2.

III.RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Comparison of AQI Values

The AQI values obtained using the three models studied are presented in Table-4. The measured values in the field for the four parameters considered along with the permissible limits are also given in Table-4 for comparison. The temperature at each of the four days of measurement is also recorded for assessment of possible AAQ variation with respect to the ambient temperature.

TABLE 4
COMPARISON OF AQI VALUES BASED ON THE THREE MODELS STUDIED

S. No	Date	Temp °C	AQI Values			Measured Values, ppm			
			Model-1	Model-2	Model-3	PM10	PM2.5	SO ₂	NO ₂
1	11/3/22	38°C	10.25	3.12	22.03	17.80	13.22	0.24	0.71
2	24/3/22	34°C	15.23	8.66	33.79	33.79	11.48	1.04	5.38
3	11/4/22	32°C	19.50	4.68	54.38	54.38	13.25	0.16	1.61
4	21/4/22	37°C	11.44	3.36	26.02	18.71	15.62	0.32	0.53
Permissible Limits, ppm						100	60	80	80

The following observations are drawn from Table-4:

- PM10 and PM2.5 are the most dominating parameters studied while the gaseous parameters show very minimum concentration during the study.
- PM10 values are inversely proportional to the ambient temperature. Maximum value of 54.35 ppm reached at 32C while minimum value of 17.8 ppm is obtained at 38C. This can be understood from the fact that as ambient temperature increases, moisture reduces and dry particles rise up in the atmosphere.
- The maximum value of PM10 is resulting in the final maximum API value of 54.35 under Model-3

(currently practiced in India). The PM_{2.5} values correspond to slightly increased API values of 22.03 and 26.02 during 11th March and 21st April respectively.

- The impact of nearby heavy vehicular movement at the sampling location is noticed on 11th April due to the relatively high concentrations of pollutants.
- The highest AQI values of 54.35 and 19.5 during 11th April computed by the Models-1 and -3 are in agreement with each other. This is due to the fact that a simple ratio of C/C_s is considered in the AQI computation in Model-1. Higher the ratio, higher will be the corresponding AQI value.
- A higher AQI value of 8.66 is observed in Model-2 on 24th March but a second highest value of 4.68 is obtained on 11th April where a higher AQI value is observed using Models 1 & 2. This is due to the logarithmic values used in the calculation. Relatively higher values of SO₂ and NO₂ are recorded on 24th March, which resulted in a slightly higher AQI value in the computation using logarithmic scale.

Based on the highest AQI values obtained from each of the three models, Mylavaram can be considered as Clean based on Model-1, Very clean based on Model-2, and Satisfactory based on Model-3. The AQI obtained at Mylavaram during a previous study [8] is in the range of 51-100 and the air quality was classified as Satisfactory (Refer Table-3). This shows that the AAQ is within the permissible limits with a Satisfactory-Clean air quality.

Assimilation Capacity Computation

The AAQ concentration for the parameters such as PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, SO₂ and NO₂ are measured analytically during four different days of sampling. The impact of plume concentration of NTTPS at Mylavaram, located at 20 km of aerial distance, is computed mathematically using Gaussian Model [17]. The data available [16] pertaining to emissions data from NTTPS is considered. A code is developed using C-programming to incorporate the Gaussian model [17, 18], Plume rise using Holland's model and Davidson & Bryant model [18,19]. Different wind speeds such as 3.34 – 15.24 m/s [16] are considered at a stack height of 240m to allow dispersion of pollutants. All the six atmospheric stability conditions such as A-F are considered to identify the worst possible scenario of emissions concentration. The code developed is used to predict (Garg, 2007) the SO₂ and SPM concentrations at Mylavaram.

The assimilation capacity is calculated as the difference between the permissible limit and the ambient concentration. The predicted values obtained are 3.1 ppm and 33 ppm for SO₂ and SPM respectively. The maximum values of SO₂ and SPM as PM₁₀ obtained using field measurement are 1.04 and 54.38 ppm respectively. The assimilation capacity at the Mylavaram is hence very high up to 76.9 ppm and 45.62 ppm if we consider the highest values from the above observations. Hence Mylavaram can be considered as a safe place at present with a good margin for assimilation of high concentration pollutants. This observation is similar to that obtained using the study with the AQI models.

IV. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

The ambient air quality (AAQ) is determined at Mylavaram, a busy town and mandal headquarter in NTR district, Andhra Pradesh, India. The Air quality index (AQI) is computed using three models and compared. It is concluded that the AQI at Mylavaram is considered as Clean-Satisfactory, which is in agreement with the AQI values determined at the same location previously. The assimilative capacity in terms of air pollution is also determined based on the permissible limits and the obtained concentration of the same pollutant at Mylavaram. For this purpose, a Code is developed using C language based on Gaussian model, Plume rise using Holland's & Davidson and Bryant models. The assimilation capacity at the Mylavaram is found to be very high up to 76.9 ppm and 45.62 ppm if we consider the highest values of

SPM (PM10) and SO₂. Hence Mylavaram can be considered as a safe place at present with a good margin for assimilation of high concentration pollutants. This observation is similar to that obtained using the study with the AQI models.

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